

RESILIENCE IN OLD AGE: CONSTRUCTION OF ACTIVE-AGING SOCIAL REALITY IN THE NGORO INDUSTRIAL PARK (NIP) AREA

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Abstract: This study employs a qualitative approach based on Berger and Luckmann's Social Reality Construction theory to identify social resilience in elderly groups in Ngoro Village and its suitability in the concept of active aging. This study addresses the social issue of elderly activity and the importance of fostering resilience in these groups. Social resilience in a more diverse group of elderly farmers in various fields, namely, economic, social, and health fields, shows the existence of a concept of self-autonomy. The positive response shown by factors external to the elderly (government, family, community) is supported. Therefore, the social resilience in the elderly group can be grouped into three main pillars of the active-aging concept, namely; Participation (elderly activities in the economic and social fields), health (family/cluster presence, integrated health post and elderly gymnastics, exercise on their own initiative), and security (BPJS, BPNT, PKH, and safe settlements).

Keywords: Active-Aging, Elderly, Resilience, Social Reality Construction

Introduction

Resilience is one of the most intriguing concepts in social life. The concept of resilience can be applied to various social contexts, one of which is the elderly population. Resilience in elderly groups has unwittingly occurred in various parts of the world, taking different forms depending on the environmental conditions surrounding their place of residence. According to the sociological perspective, resilience can be defined as the ability or effort of a social system to maintain its social integrity or integration when and/or after receiving internal and external disturbances (Kinseng, 2019). One aspect of resilience is adaptation. One example is the adaptation carried out by the elderly in nursing homes as a new environment (Karni, A., 2019). In addition to adaptation, awareness is another important aspect of resilience. The awareness of living alone among the elderly in Iran impacts improving their quality of life. The fact that the majority of the elderly spend their free time to remain productive evidenced awareness as an important of resilience. (Kourayem and Mahmoodinia, 2021). This condition is just one example of the many ways in which the elderly around the world demonstrate resilience. On the other hand, the elderly can improve their quality of life by regularly checking their health conditions, being grateful, and actively

participating in social activities in their community (Indrawati, L et al., 2023). These activities also lead to a form of resilience that the elderly group can perform. Resilience carried out by the elderly also has a relationship with their psychological well-being (Pratama, A. F. and Murtiyani, N., 2023). Therefore, in this study, resilience can be interpreted as a form of awareness carried out by a social system to maintain its role and existence in the social environment. Through a survey conducted by the Lloyd’s Register Foundation in 2024 (19/06/2024), the following data were obtained:

Figure 1: Elderly survivorship survey

Source: Lloyd’s Register Foundation, 2024.

From 142 countries that participated in the survey, the top 10 countries with the ability to survive the elderly without income were obtained. Norway has the highest elderly survival rate, where 93% of people aged 65 years and over can fulfill their needs for a period of 4 months or more without income. This can happen when the government enforces laws and policies that provide benefits to all people, especially the elderly. For example, the Norwegian Employment and Welfare Administration (NAV) offers various programs that support individuals up to the age of 67, including adjustments to qualifications and vocational training. By providing a guaranteed pension to its people, the government provides an opportunity for the elderly to increase their life expectancy. Supported by health access and special housing for the elderly. In addition to Norway, an almost similar policy is implemented in Japan, namely, a policy for companies in the country to rehire the elderly. These several factors, including: increasing life expectancy, increasing company productivity, transferring expertise, and cheaper salaries motivated the government creates policies that provide benefits to all people, especially the elderly. (Suryadi, 2019). The difference in the happiness conditions of the elderly when they are still actively working and when they are no longer working (Jamalludin, 2021) is another factor that also motivates post-retirement elderly workers to decide to return to work. It is unfortunate that some countries still do not have legislation that thoroughly and in detail accommodates the needs of the elderly group.

Through the concept of active aging, the phenomenon of resilience in the elderly can be carefully identified by referring to the pillars of the concept. In 2002, the World Health Organization defined active aging as an effort to improve the quality of life of older people as they age, a process of optimizing opportunities for health, participation, and security (Hakim, 2020). In this concept, the elderly are no longer a “burden” but how can they remain productive at their age? The Active-Aging concept has 3 main pillars of the policy framework (WHO, 2002, p. 45): Participation, Health, and Security, which can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 2: Three Pillars of active-aging policy framework

Source: WHO, 2002, p. 45

One of the success factors in implementing the active-aging concept for the elderly is a safe settlement pattern. One example is the community-based settlement (Helgetun) in Western Norway. These settlements can create a sense of security for the elderly. A special elderly settlement program can be realized when there is a legal umbrella and regulations that oversee it (Forsund et al., 2024). The applicable regulations in Norway have been able to accommodate the needs of the elderly. Successful aging emphasizes activity, productivity, and freedom of choice. In particular, the ease with which older people can access public services (Blix & Ågotnes, 2023). Active-aging can be interpreted as a form of resilience activity carried out by the elderly by referring to the important concepts contained in it.

According to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), the dependency ratio of the elderly population in Indonesia reached 16.09 points in 2022 (21/06/2023). Based on these data, it appears that there is a decrease in the elderly dependency rate, when compared to 2021, the elderly dependency ratio in Indonesia decreased by 0.67 points in 2022 compared to 2021. This reflects the potential to improve the quality of life of the elderly in Indonesia. As a result, more research is needed to identify the factors driving the decline in the elderly dependency rate, such as changes in the elderly population's lifestyle and health. However, the rapid growth of businesses in Indonesia's industrial estates undoubtedly impacts the local community. Besides the ability to create new jobs, the loss of green agricultural land, which is typically managed by elderly farmers, is another impact of this development. For example, investors have transformed the Ngoro Industrial Park area, which used to be covered in green agricultural land, into sturdy buildings with towering chimneys in the center. Rice fields are shrinking, forcing the elderly who used to work as farmers to shift to other occupations. Furthermore, to survive, they must seek alternative sources of income. Resilience refers to the efforts of an elderly group to meet their basic needs.

The strategic location of Ngoro Village supports the desire of the elderly to continue to actively participate. The global phenomenon of resilience has distinct characteristics, including how the social reality of elderly community groups can be formed and applied in their current social context. This study aims to reveal how the development of social resilience in elderly groups and communities in Ngoro Village can promote the success of resilience carried out by elderly groups in various fields on a consistent and reviewed basis using the concept of active aging. This is also related to previous research on the resilience of elderly populations, which are typically fully supported by the state. In this study, exploring support from the social environment can produce resilience in more diverse elderly groups.

Methods

This study used a descriptive qualitative approach. The qualitative approach emphasizes meaning and deep understanding, reasoning, and definition of a situation and prioritizes the process (Creswell and Wekke, 2020). The researcher chose the descriptive qualitative method because the researcher wanted to more specifically, transparently, and in depth describe the situation of the elderly group to be observed in Ngoro Village. This study used a phenomenological research design with SRC theory developed by Peter L Berger and Thomas Luckmann. The theory was chosen with the consideration that elderly resilience through the concept of active aging is a construction of social reality from social actors, which will be reviewed through 3 main phases, namely, Objectivation, Internalization (Institutionalization), and Externalization (Berger & Luckmann, 1991). Through this theory, the researcher wants to see the perspective of the elderly group around the NIP area regarding the resilience efforts made after they have switched to another livelihood sector. The difference between this study and the previous study is how the phenomenon of resilience in the elderly will be analyzed using the perspective of social reality construction and the concept of active-aging with environmental conditions around the industrial area.

This study was conducted in Ngoro Village, Ngoro Sub-district, Mojokerto District. Ngoro Village is located in the Ngoro Industrial Park (NIP) area. There are several reasons for choosing Ngoro Village as the research location. First, many elderly people who used to work as farmers are no longer working as farmers, so they are living their old age by switching professions and performing various life activities. Second, the elderly in Ngoro Village see opportunities for economic activities in Ngoro Village, supported by the village's strategic location around the Ngoro Industrial Park (NIP) area. Third, the geographical location of their settlements is close, and a form of resilience emerges in the elderly group with the same fateful background from the social interactions that are established. Therefore, indirectly, the form of resilience carried out by the elderly group is supported by the environment around them. The data sources in this study were divided into primary data sources (the elderly, the head of the village, village midwife staff, Ngoro village figures, village monographic data, and elderly population data) and secondary data sources (literature studies in the form of journals relevant to the research, e-books that discuss social resilience, active-aging, and social reality construction theory, and some news spread in online mass media).

The research subjects in this study were the elderly group around the Ngoro Industrial Park (NIP) area, totaling 8 people. Purposive sampling was used to select the eight research subjects. The research subjects were selected with the following considerations: (1) elderly who were once farmers and now have switched professions and live alone; elderly A (73 years old) female, boarding house owner; elderly B (81 years old) male, rent owner; (2) elderly couples who used to work as farmers and are now active in other sectors; elderly C (80 years old) male and D (70 years old) female, owning a grocery store and breeding chickens and ducks; elderly E (71 years old) male and F (66 years old) female, working in catering and selling chicken feed; elderly G (70 years old) male and H (67 years old) female, working as cattle and goat breeders. The informants were selected using a purposive sampling technique where researchers selected several elderly farmers with certain criteria and could provide information and their perspectives on the resilience of the elderly group viewed through the concept of active aging. Data collection in this study was performed using several techniques, including (1) observation, which consists of participatory and non-participatory observation, (2) in-depth interviews, (3) documentation, and (4) literature study relevant to the research theme. The researchers performed participatory observation by staying in the elderly home 1-2 days. Researchers participated in activities with the elderly under study. The data analysis technique used was from Miles and Huberman. Data analysis consists of 4 stages, namely data collection in the

field, data presentation, which will then be condensed, and conclusion drawing. In this study, data validity checks were conducted. This was done to confirm that the data obtained were in accordance with the events in the field without being reduced or exaggerated. The researchers performed data validation by source and method triangulation.

Results and Discussion

Demographical and Geographical Conditions of the Ngoro Village

Based on the monographic data of Ngoro Village, the geographical and demographic conditions of Ngoro Village are described below: Ngoro Village is one of 19 villages in Ngoro District. Ngoro has a fairly large area. Ngoro has an area of 3.35km², equivalent to 5.53% of the total area of Ngoro District. It consists of 5 RW and 38 RT with a total population of 5,944 people. The male and female populations are 2,979 and 2,965, respectively. The number of elderly people is 711, with 331 elderly men and 380 elderly women. The elderly data obtained are from residents with an age classification of 60 years and over. Meanwhile, there are 300 elderly recipients of BPNT (Non-Cash Food Assistance) assistance is 300 elderly and the number of PKH (Family Hope Program) beneficiaries is 150 elderly. Both programs are received through an account that has been given to the recipients, so all assistance received has been in non-cash form. Ngoro Village has the highest number of primary schools, with four schools. In 2022/2023, Ngoro village had the highest number of primary school students (750). Ngoro village has five mosques, 16 prayer rooms, and two churches.

The Ngoro District has an industrial area of approximately 500 hectares. Three factories have been developed in Ngoro Village in the industrial sector. The CLEO plant is one of them. To expand its production space, PT Sariguna Primatirta Tbk (CLEO), the issuer of bottled drinking water, revealed that it had invested in the purchase of 10,809 m² of land in 2019.

Based on the research results obtained from interviews with research subjects, field data were obtained regarding the form of social resilience carried out by the elderly group. The forms of resilience in the elderly group in Ngoro Village are quite diverse, and each research subject has a different construction.

An overview of the social resilience of the elderly in Ngoro Village

In this study, the social resilience of the elderly group in Ngoro Village was identified from their various community lives, including the following:

Economic Resilience

The economy is one of the most important aspects in people's lives. It is the main umbrella for the elderly group's goals in performing resilience. Seeing the conditions in the field, the research participants in this study have each activity oriented toward economic fulfillment. For elderly couples C and D, the economic activity involves opening a grocery store. The target consumers are residents of boarding houses that are mostly employees of the CLEO factory around the house of elderly couple C and D. Elderly C said (interview 30/03/24):

Indeed, the average buyer is the boarding house residents, right in the front, the right-left side is also a boarding house, so I made the shop by looking at that opportunity...

Elderly C schedules the purchase of store stock within 2 weeks. The researcher was given the opportunity to assist in the process of purchasing grocery store stock. In addition, Elderly D has several farm animals, including chickens and ducks. Income earned from livestock activities is uncertain, depending on the market price of livestock when they are sold. In addition, C and D are permanent recipients of BPNT (Non-Cash Food Assistance) and PKH (Family Hope Program), which are programs from the government. The procedure for distributing assistance has also been conducted digitally/non-cash. Elderly E and F, who are also elderly couples, have some

differences from elderly C and D. Elderly F goes to work at a catering service every morning and returns from work in the afternoon depending on the number of orders at the catering service. Almost every day, the elderly F home brings leftover rice from the catering service. It led to a business idea from both of them. The leftover rice will be dried and sold as chicken feed. Elderly F said (interview 13/09/24):

Yes, at first, it was a whim because my husband was not doing anything. The leftover rice that I got was also quite a lot, so we tried drying it and sell it.

Elderly E and F have more money because of these activities. They were able to purchase a weighing device after a spontaneous idea to use leftover rice. Elderly E has no steady work since the sale of the rice farms. As a result, the elderly E started a modest animal feed company that has grown quickly to this point. Regular clients already purchase chicken feed from E and F. Weather is the largest barrier. E and F can produce 10–20 kg of animal feed every week during the dry season. During the rainy season, only 5–10 kg of animal feed is produced per week. Even though the demand for animal feed is quite high, it still cannot be met during the rainy season. Animal feed owned by elderly E and F is sold at a price range of Rp4, 500-Rp5, 000/kg depending on the drying time. The economic activities carried out by E and F are based on the desire to remain active in their aging years. The children of E and F have also offered to live with one of their children. However, both of them refused it because they could not afford to leave the house they lived in.

The next elderly couple is also involved in livestock activities. G and H own 4 cows and 6 goats. Both of them decided to build a cage on their property, which is not far from the house in which they live. The reason is so that they can remain consistent in their activities. To reach their cattle barn, elderly G and H pedal their bicycle, and it takes about 5 to 10 minutes to reach their cattle barn. The income earned from livestock activities is partly saved, and the rest is used for daily life. A significant difference is observed in the elderly who live alone. A decided to build a boarding house behind her house after her husband died. Apart from fulfilling her daily needs, Elderly A chose to build a boarding house so that there are still many people around her house. Elderly A mentioned that the boarding house business would be quite promising by looking at the economic potential in Ngoro Village, which is strategically located around the Ngoro Industrial Park area. Elderly A said (interview, 24/09/14):

The rice fields were initially requested to be sold and turned into a factory. Then, I started thinking about what business would be good, and I considered making a boarding house because the factory employees would also come from various regions.

Elderly A has 8 boarding rooms, and there are only 2 empty rooms. Elderly G's boarding house costs IDR 500,000 per room per month and has a kitchen for cooking, Wi-Fi, and shared restrooms. Elderly B engages in economic activity by renting out his home, which is not all that different from that of elderly A. Elderly B felt lonely after losing his partner and needed a discussion partner. As a result, the elderly B decided to rent out his house with a note that he still lived there. The concept of renting is more similar to boarding houses. There are 4 rooms for rent. The tenants were initially dominated by women, but the house now only accepts male residents, along with negative responses from some of the surrounding neighbors. The monthly rent is around Rp400, 000 and includes a refrigerator, bathroom, WiFi, and kitchen facilities. Elderly B said that his decision to rent out his house was the right one because he can interact with the tenants and receive their encouragement to continue living.

Social Resilience

In addition to the economic sector, participation in the social environment is a form of social resilience carried out by the elderly group in Ngoro Village. Although they are no longer young, the elderly women in Ngoro

Village still actively participate in the empowerment and family welfare (PKK) social gatherings. The main reason for the existence of social gatherings is as a means of interacting with PKK members. Based on the data obtained from interviews with D, weekly social gathering activities can be an alternative to relieve stress and loneliness. Elderly D said (interview 13/09/24):

For me, I have always liked to join social gatherings like this, because it is nice to meet friends and chat. So even though I am at this age, I still like to get together like this.

Being able to talk and exchange information with peers and younger people makes D feel better. In addition to Elderly D, a member of the PKK's social gathering, Elderly A, who lives alone, is also a member. Before Elderly A's health condition deteriorated, she was quite active in social activities in Ngoro Village. However, after her health condition declined some time ago, Elderly a now prefers to chat with her neighbors. Relatives and neighbors also routinely visit the house of the elderly A. Meanwhile, F, an elderly woman who works in the catering industry, is rarely seen participating in the PKK's social gatherings. Apart from the difficulty in managing her time, she is also tired because she has been working all day. Elderly F often chooses to visit her grandchildren that are not far from her house.

On the other hand, the male elderly are no less active in their social environment. Elderly C consistently participates in routine community service activities and house-building collective work activities. The bond between residents in Ngoro Village is fairly good. When a neighbor builds a house, the residents work together to help with the construction process. From teenagers, adults, to the elderly, they all help build the house. Elderly C also revealed that community service and collective work activities could revive his spirit. Elderly C still feels happy because he can still help others. In contrast to elderly C, elderly E prefers to interact with the local residents only as needed. This is due to the condition of Elder E's body, which is more vulnerable, and he is not recommended to lift heavy loads. Elderly B is a type of community member who is reluctant to see his environment dirty. Therefore, B always routinely cleans his house both in the morning and in the evening. Elderly B used to read newspapers and books, but now her reading has started to decrease because her eyesight has begun to deteriorate. Elderly B said (interview 27/09/24):

...I used to read newspapers, books, and magazines. Now I get dizzy if I look at the text for too long, and I am already old. But I still take the time to read for a while.

Before their spouse died, Elderly B and his wife were a harmonious couple. Both of them would ride a bicycle to the rice fields in the morning while chatting and greeting their neighbors. However, after the death of his wife, Elderly B began to look gloomy and sad. Fortunately, the condition of Elderly B has improved since his house was rented out.

In addition, from a socio-spiritual perspective, the elderly also carry out several other social activities. The elderly tend to improve their relationship with God during their aging period. This is evidenced by the scene discovered by researchers during field observations. The location of Musholla, which is close to residential areas, adds to the elderly group's ease of access to worship in the congregation. Elderly C is one of the most routine prayer attendees who pray in the Musholla near his house. He always gets ready half an hour before the call to prayer. Followed by other elderly people who also gathered to pray in the congregation. Religious activities in Ngoro Village during Ramadan. Elderly C and D, who are no longer young, still perform their obligations as Muslims to fast for a full day. They wake up early in the morning to prepare the Suhoor menu. After the call for Fajr prayer, C and D go to the mosque and continue with the Quran reading activity.

Other social-spiritual activities that are also widely participated in by the elderly are routine religious activities that are held once a week. Women's and men's religious activities are held on different days. The elderly are quite active in participating in these activities because, in addition to strengthening faith in the religious activities, it can also be used as a place to chat among fellow elderly. Routine religious activities are found in many communities. However, the consistency shown by the elderly in participating in these activities is an important point. In addition, the elderly can relieve the feeling of loneliness that often comes through religious activities. Boredom and loneliness are the things most often experienced by the elderly. Based on the results of interviews conducted with the research subjects, one of the elderly mentioned that traveling to a tourism destination can alleviate the boredom that comes to him. For the elderly A, the location to be visited is not the main thing, but how he can still feel a new atmosphere in the tourist attractions. Not only elderly A as elderly who lives alone, but elderly couples also feel the same way. Through recreation/tourism activities, elderly groups can do various activities, including shopping, sightseeing, and cooking. In line with the high interest of the elderly group, one resident becomes the coordinator and schedules recreational activities every year. Religious tourism sites such as the Walisongo pilgrimage and the Cheng Ho Mosque are often visited. Not only religious tourism sites, the elderly also often tourist destinations such as furniture markets and several places that have not been visited. The form of resilience of the elderly is reflected through their desire to continue participating in tourism activities to fill their spare time.

Socio-politics is another social dimension that also exists in society. During their aging period, some elderly people still consistently involve themselves in political contestation. One of them is the elderly E, who has become a member of the success team of the candidates several times. Together with his son, the elderly E participated in the campaign and sought support for the candidates of the party he supported. It can encourage the enthusiasm of the elderly.

Health Resilience

The government contributes to this field through several programs intended for the elderly. The first program that is quite easy to find is the integrated healthcare post (posyandu) for the elderly. The researchers had the opportunity to accompany one of the elderly participants, Elderly D. In the integrated healthcare post, there are several services for the elderly, including blood tests, blood sugar tests, and consultations. Based on initial interviews with midwives and staff in Ngoro Village, an integrated healthcare post for the elderly is held once a month. However, the implementation schedule is adjusted to the free schedule of the village midwives. Integrated healthcare post activities are conducted for 3 days in rotation with the children's integrated healthcare post. An integrated healthcare post for the elderly is not only a free healthcare service but also a place for the elderly to meet their peers. They talk to each other and share stories. Based on the obtained monographic data, the number of elderly people in Ngoro Village is 711. It is a fairly large number on a village scale. In addition to the integrated healthcare post, an elderly exercise program under the auspices of the elderly volunteers in Ngoro Village is available. The exercise program for the elderly is held once a week at the village hall in Ngoro Village. Every elderly person who comes to the integrated health post brings a special book that has been distributed by the village office to record the results of the tests conducted. After that, the elderly will be invited to measure their weight and height, followed by blood pressure and blood sugar. Elderly participants D, F, and A revealed that they often participate in elderly exercise organized by elderly volunteers. Elderly exercise participants were dominated by elderly women.

On the other hand, H rarely attends elderly exercise activities and integrated healthcare posts (posyandu) for the elderly. This is due to the mind-set of the elderly, H, who prefers herbal medicine and routine simple exercises. G and H greatly minimize the habit of checking into clinics, especially hospitals, among elderly couples. She does not want to inconvenience her children. Elderly H said (interview 14/09/24):

It's rare for me and my husband to go to the integrated healthcare post. We usually just drink herbal medicine and eat healthy foods. Not those that use MSG, because I also don't want to be sick and bother my children.

Government programs in the health sector are inseparable from the BPJS (Social Security Organizing Agency) program. The majority of the elderly in Ngoro Village already have a BPJS card. All the participants had a BPJS card. The BPJS program has been able to protect the health sector's needs of the elderly group. Elderly couples C and D revealed that the BPJS is very helpful. When their health condition worsens and further action is required, they do not have to worry about costs. However, for hospitalization and medical check-ups, the community must first arrange a referral letter at the community health center. Meanwhile, elderly individuals, both couples and singles, do not understand the procedure for submitting a referral letter. Therefore, elderly couples C and D often ask their children/grandchildren for help in obtaining referral letters from the community health center. Likewise, elderly E, with her congenital asthma disease, requires regular check-ups when her health condition declines. Elderly E said (interview 13/09/24):

Fortunately, there is BPJS, so we can be treated immediately without worrying about the costs, especially if my asthma relapses.

In Elderly E's condition, advice has been given that smoking is not allowed. However, the prohibition is often ignored by the elderly. At some point, E's condition worsened and he had to receive further hospital treatment. The incurred costs were fully covered through BPJS.

The senior citizens of Ngoro Village, in addition to the government programs offered, understand the value of being physically healthy as they age. As previously mentioned, starting from routine jogging activities every morning carried out by Elderly C before starting activities, sunbathing in the morning sun, cycling, and maintaining a good diet. The senior population of Ngoro Village can lead active lifestyles because they are conscious of the need to preserve their physical health.

Construction of Active-Aging Social Resilience in the Ngoro Village Elderly Group

The social resilience of the elderly in Ngoro Village is inseparable from the many factors that support their active participation in their social environment. Through the concept of active aging and the three main pillars that indicate that a person is experiencing active aging, namely: participation, health, and security. Participation is reflected in the elderly in Ngoro Village through various social activities. The decision of the elderly to continue to participate in their social environment is also inseparable from the positive response given by the surrounding community. As mentioned, the fulfilment of all needs and desires balanced with the support of the surrounding environment can have an impact on the decision of the elderly to continue to actively contribute to the surrounding environment. Both income-generating activities and other social activities (WHO, 2002 p. 46).

It also reflects how Indonesian society tends to apply high social values to its social environment. The resilience of the elderly group in the Ngoro Village community is reflected in various types of resilience activities, ranging from community service to recreational activities that consistently involve the elderly group. Apart from the socio-spiritual and socio-recreational activities that get high enthusiasm from the involvement of the elderly, socio-political activities are also carried out by the elderly as a form of social resilience. The participation of the elderly in the political contestation agenda can still be found in Ngoro Village, although very rare. The community's

interest in the socio-political field, which decreases with age, is also a form of social reality that exists within each elderly person. Nevertheless, many elderly people in other areas still play an active role in socio-political activities.

On the other hand, the physical condition of the elderly who have decreased is always monitored through a program provided by the government, namely, integrated healthcare post for the elderly. In terms of health, the government's presence in facilitating the rights of the elderly group continues to be very significant, although in the integrated healthcare post for the elderly, not a few choose not to participate in these activities. In addition to the integrated healthcare post for the elderly, an exercise program for the elderly aims to maintain their physical fitness. The elderly exercise program, which is mostly attended by elderly women, is one of the facilities that can be utilized by the elderly to keep exercising during their aging period. In addition, the awareness of the elderly in maintaining physical fitness is evident in the habits of some elderly people who routinely do light stretching, sunbathing in the morning sun, jogging, and walking around their backyards.

The point of health in the active-aging concept refers to how the balance conditions in the lives of the elderly. In addition to paying attention to the physical health conditions of the elderly, the elderly still receive positive support from the surrounding environment, especially in some conditions that require further treatment. The presence of family, household helpers, and relatives plays an important role in fostering the elderly's desire to recover soon when their condition declines. It can be seen from the closeness that exists between the elderly by visiting other elderly who are in the recovery phase. They provide moral support by accompanying the elderly so that they do not feel lonely and left behind. This condition can form a balance within the elderly, between the disease suffered and the support given to the elderly will foster the desire of the elderly to live a healthy life and be able to live independently in active aging (WHO, 2002 p. 45-46), and take some of their time to continue to actively participate in their social environment.

Meanwhile, the point of security in the active-aging concept tends to be how the government provides adequate social security to the elderly. The social security program that has been felt by the elderly so far is through BPJS. The ease with which the elderly can access all forms of health and social facilities, as well as other needs, is also one of the conditions for the creation of AAD in the elderly. When the elderly have to take care of referral letters for medical check-ups or further treatment at the community healthcare center, the elderly need assistance and must ask for help from family or neighbors to take care of referral letters at the nearest community healthcare center. Under these conditions, the elderly in Ngoro Village benefit from the close-knit community in which they live. Supportive housing conditions create a safe and comfortable environment for the elderly. The entire community in Ngoro Village respects, supports, and works together in all social activities. The settlement conditions in Ngoro Village are similar to those in community-based settlements (Helgetun) in Western Norway. As mentioned, one of the success factors in implementing the active-aging concept for the elderly is a safe settlement concept. These settlements can create a sense of security for the elderly. Including in-depth experiences regarding how to take care of themselves and with the post-COVID-19 experience, the elderly have social involvement with each other (Førsund et al., 2024). The difference is how the existing housing conditions in Norway are facilitated by the government and specialized for the elderly. In Indonesia, it is very rarely found, and the current government program is still only focused on the social security side of the community through the BPJS program, which includes the elderly group. In addition to the BPJS program, the government provides welfare guarantees to the elderly through the BPNT and PKH programs. Furthermore, the settlement model in

Ngoro Village can become a comfortable environment because of the social construction built by the elderly and the community.

The Ngoro community’s positive social support for the elderly brings happiness to the various parties involved in community life. In the Ngoro Village community, the peace and happiness that emerge from the social interactions between residents go beyond happiness measured solely by economic achievement. On the other hand, the SNHI (Sustainable Neighbourhoods for Happiness Index) approach is used in the United States to analyse several cities in the application of sustainable neighbourhoods and achieve the goal of creating happiness in the community that exceeds the ambition of economic achievement in each individual. The enhanced SNHI has only been successfully applied to neighbourhoods in the southwestern United States. (Mitra et al., 2019). Meanwhile, in the Ngoro Village, each individual’s awareness creates an environment that prioritizes harmony and helping each other. The people of Ngoro Village also tend to ignore each individual’s economic background when they need help. Therefore, a positive social construction is formed and can support the elderly group’s consistency in carrying out various activities in their social environment.

The construction process of the resilience of the elderly group in Ngoro Village through the concept of active aging can be seen in the following diagram:

Figure 3: Construction scheme of active-aging social resilience in the elderly

Source: Researcher, 2024

In the scheme above, the construction of active-aging social reality in the elderly group appears to be carried out through 3 construction processes: objectivation, internalization (institutionalization), and externalization involving the government, family, and society. In this context, the community refers to elderly former farmers who geographically reside in the area around the Ngoro Industrial Park (NIP), which can be considered an industrialization area. Therefore, they produce different social constructions in their social environment through the circumstances experienced. The forms of social resilience carried out by the elderly in Ngoro Village have a lot of diversity and are spread in various fields.

As a form of social reality construction, social resilience activities carried out by the elderly in Ngoro Village are formed through various experiences, values, and social norms that exist in society that are adopted, and interpreted. Thus, they experience signification and transform it into a habit or habitualization. After experiencing this process, new social values emerge as a form of internalization and are passed on to the next generation through the externalization process. The social reality construction process experienced by the elderly in Ngoro Village is

reviewed through 3 processes contained in the theory of social reality construction developed by Peter L Berger and Thomas Luckmann: Objectivation, Internalization (Institutionalization), and Externalization. Social construction in society cannot be formed without the support and role of external factors such as government, family, and society. In the objectivation process, the conditions in each family structure and the social norms in the surrounding community form a situation that encourages social resilience in the elderly. The experiences adopted by the social environment of the elderly supported the desire that arises in the elderly to live independently and actively participate. Based on the experience of a farmer who is active in activities, the elderly have the desire to continue to have activities in their old age. Through this experience, even though the elderly are no longer able to live as farmers due to the rice fields that have been sold, they have switched to other professions. The transition of professions carried out by the elderly is mostly based on what they have been able to do, as one example of some elderly people's economic activities. Economic activities refer to how opportunities are created by industrial development in Ngoro Village. With these opportunities, the elderly began to open boarding houses and grocery stores, and the target market was factory employees around Ngoro Village and the Ngoro Industrial Park area. Various decisions taken by the elderly by building boarding houses or renting out their homes, have the support of their families and the surrounding community. The elderly need the presence of other humans to accompany them. No matter how independent a person is, they will still need the help of other humans.

The profession switch made by the elderly is mostly in the entrepreneurship field. This refers to the age limit set for the acceptance of employees of companies and factories in Indonesia. This condition is inversely proportional to the elderly in Japan. The company in Japan even hired many elderly workers during their retirement. It was motivated by an appeal given by the government to the community to hire retired elderly people to increase company productivity, transfer expertise and relatively cheaper salaries (Suryadi, 2019). The situation in Japan is very different from the policies in Indonesia. The age limit set in Indonesia is evidence that the elderly group has limitations in participating in the economic field. Therefore, the elderly in Ngoro Village prefer to engage in entrepreneurship.

The Japanese government's policy to continue employing the elderly. Experiences adopted by the social environment of the elderly meanwhile, in Indonesia, the number of births continues to increase, requiring the elderly population to be replaced by the productive age population. Therefore, with all the limitations possessed by the elderly group, they have the awareness to perform social resilience for their sustainability. While Japan has indirectly facilitated social resilience activities by re-employing retired elderly people, the elderly themselves are involved in community activities through social resilience in Indonesia. One of the important differences between the conditions of one country and another is

In the next phase, the process of internalization (institutionalization) is carried out by the elderly. It refers to how institutionalized experiences and social norms are then interpreted and signified in everyday life. The elderly are gradually experiencing positive progress in the process of switching professions, where the elderly can familiarize themselves with their identity as entrepreneurs. Morning routines that used to be done in the rice fields now turn to other activities, such as morning exercise, spiritual activities, and animal husbandry activities. The habits that shape the identity of the elderly are followed by the government's participation in various programs that continue to develop. One of them is the integrated healthcare post (posyandu) program for the elderly. As a form of facility provided to the elderly by the government. The elderly in Ngoro Village show positive enthusiasm. Previously, it was known that the factor influencing the interest of the elderly in participating in integrated healthcare post is

that behavioral control affects the intention of the elderly to actively participate in integrated healthcare post activities (Mindianata, 2018). However, based on the findings, the elderly actively participated in integrated health post activities in addition to conducting routine health checks and meeting and chatting with their peers. This shows that the construction of social reality in the elderly has increased with the implied value in various forms of activities carried out and leads to positive things. In addition, the social interaction that exists between the elderly during the implementation of the integrated health post supports the statement that social networks or relationships are one form of factor that affects the resilience of the elderly (Sudrajat, A et al., 2023).

Apart from the integrated healthcare post for the elderly, the government also provides assistance programs to the elderly through the Non-Cash Food Assistance and the Family Hope Program. The village administration selects the elderly who receive this assistance with several requirements and considerations. According to the information obtained, not all elderly people in Ngoro Village receive social assistance to support their welfare. It shows that the program still has weaknesses. Thus, the government needs to optimize coverage and increase the benefits of PKH and BPNT by mapping the characteristics of the area and the individual characteristics of prospective recipients (Kuntarto, T. and Hanri, M., 2023), which will greatly help the sustainability of the program.

Some of the findings show that Law Number 13 of 1998 concerning the Welfare of the Elderly (UU Lansia) has not been able to answer the challenges faced by the complexity of elderly problems in the future regarding weak data collection related to recipients of social assistance from the government (Hakim, 2020). It is followed by the performance of ministries/agencies from both the central and regional levels that have not been well integrated, which is shown in the regulation of assistance through the bank accounts that have been distributed. Social assistance, which is said to be distributed every month, will only be informed to elderly recipients a few months later, so the integration between the central and regional governments needs to be addressed again. Meanwhile, some findings indicate that the law has not been maximized in accommodating the rights of the elderly. The BPJS program, as a form of social security provided by the government to the elderly, is evidence that the government continues to improve in accommodating the rights of the elderly. The benefits of the BPJS program have been felt by almost all groups of people, not only the elderly. In Ngoro Village, most of the hospital treatment costs have been fully covered by the BPJS program.

In addition to the presence of the government through various programs, the presence of family and community also plays a role in the process of internalization (institutionalization) of the construction of the elderly's social reality. Although the presence of the family tends to be minimal in some conditions, the elderly still feel it. In general, the elderly cannot be separated from 3 things, namely, poverty, neglect, and protection which are the main problems for each elderly (Putri, I. N. R. and Afifah, W., 2022). However, the conditions in the field revealed that some of the elderly actually decided to live alone because they did not want to burden their children. The elderly still feel the presence of the family. It is common for the elderly's family, be it children, grandchildren, or great-grandchildren, to visit to check on the elderly's condition. Especially when the physical condition of the elderly decreases and requires further hospital treatment, the elderly family will always accompany them. Meanwhile, the community plays a role in providing moral support for all positive activities carried out by the elderly. The support provided by the surrounding environment can reduce the negative perception of the elderly that they are abandoned or even excluded from social life. The realization of comfortable and safe settlements for the elderly is also a form of the role of the Ngoro Village community, so that the elderly can actively participate in their social environment.

The last process in the formation of social reality construction is the externalization process. Habits that have undergone continuous signification create new values in society. It is then passed on to the next generation. One example is from the activities of the elderly in the social field. In community service activities, the elderly involve themselves not only as a form of obligation as a community but also to alleviate loneliness. Apart from community service activities, externalization can be seen in socio-spiritual activities. Elderly people with limited physical conditions still perform their obligations as good religious people. Through other social-spiritual activities, such as routine religious activities, the elderly can strengthen their faith while meeting and greeting their peers. The same applies to socio-recreational and socio-political activities.

The construction of social reality created by the elderly through various forms of activities in the community has implied values that can be seen from how the elderly actively participate in their social environment. Active participation of the elderly with all their physical limitations can be a form of resilience within the elderly group. Through the construction of social reality carried out by the elderly in Ngoro Village, the elderly have an active aging orientation, including a positive mindset, a healthy lifestyle, and the physical condition of the elderly who are still fit at an old age. It also has an impact on the surrounding community, where the elderly group can provide a picture of active aging that can be applied in social life through a variety of social resilience. Social resilience in the elderly group in Ngoro Village is also inseparable from the support provided by external factors, including the government, family, and community, to create a positive and safe settlement. The safety and comfort felt by the elderly in their place of residence helps them to continue to actively participate.

Conclusion

This study successfully revealed the social reality of active-aging as a social resilience of older former farmers in the Ngoro Industrial Park (NIP) area. The three processes in social reality construction theory and the three main pillars of the active-aging concept, which are represented in the forms of social resilience among the elderly population in Ngoro Village, were examined by the researcher from the perspective of social reality construction theory.

The aspects showing that social resilience in elderly former farmers in Ngoro Village is more diverse illustrate that resilience in the elderly is a form of self-autonomy. In this context, the concept of self-autonomy is that while in other countries, the resilience of the elderly tends to be facilitated and dependent on the state, in Indonesia, the form of social resilience of the elderly combines facilities from the state and the resilience that arises from their self-awareness. Thus, the forms of social resilience found in the elderly group in Ngoro Village are more diverse. Furthermore, this study shows that one crucial factor in helping the elderly attain active aging through social resilience is the way they create their social reality. The three main pillars in the concept of active aging (participation, health, and security) in the elderly in Indonesia cannot be limited to just one pillar. This is due to the connection between the activities of the elderly in one field and another. The elderly also socially interpreted the integrated healthcare post activities, which are classified as health. Economic activities carried out by the elderly (such as boarding houses and rented businesses) are also socially interpreted by the elderly. In practice, they are not only oriented toward the economic sector. This interpretation strengthens the resilience of the elderly. The social construction process in society is not instant and requires consistency in its application. The social values that exist in Indonesia are reflected through the construction of social reality in the community in Ngoro Village. The care and solidarity between people in Ngoro Village is the key to cohesion in the social environment. It also has an impact on the elderly group with all the limitations they have, they are able to overcome them through social resilience activities.

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